

Estimating the Impact of the Lebanese Economic Crisis on Employee Turnover through Motivation among other mediating variables as impeded by COVID-19

By

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Abstract

Exploratory sequential research has been conducted using an abductive approach, seeking to develop a theory by linking the direct effects of the Lebanese Economic Crisis on employee turnover, via motivation, through testing it. The tested data was collected before the pandemic started. Yet, the results under COVID-19 still apply. Initially, the data was mainly gathered through unstructured interviews targeting important decision-makers in key firms across several sectors. For this purpose, the educational, banking, hospitality, and tourism sectors were observed. The results were interpreted in parallel with a pilot study conducted to address a questionnaire using a quantitative approach to triangulate the collected data with the interview questions and the literature review. Finally, through this study, the relationship between economic crisis and employee motivation is made clearer. Recommendations on how organizations could boost employee satisfaction to limit turnover are provided.

Keywords: Political uncertainty, Employee motivation, Turnover policies, Lebanon, COVID-19.

Introduction

Theoretical Background

It is considered unethical to lay off workers during economic crises in general. Yet, there were several unethical layoff cases reported in Lebanon during the past two years (Kim, 2005; Majzoub, 2018) as the study aims to estimate the relationship between the Lebanese Economic Crisis (Independent Variable) and employee turnover (Dependent Variable), taking into account employee motivation (Mediating Variable). For this purpose, the pragmatic philosophy and the abductive approaches were used (more will be discussed in the research methodology section) in this research, as they best describe the viewpoint this study aims to reach. More variables will be applied in the study as it seeks to understand this causal relationship (Melkonian, 2020). Massive layoffs have accompanied past economic crises worldwide (Kalliath & Beck, 2001). Yet, in the long run, high employee turnover often negatively affects businesses, in which employee satisfaction and morale, productivity, efficiency, and profitability are negatively impacted (Griffin et al., 2001). Since this research sets out to depict the connection between "the

2019 Lebanese Economic Crisis" and "Employee Motivation," this relationship will be made more explicit in our literature review.

We have included in our discussion the messages that the 2020 World Economic Forum recommended to work on for the upcoming years. These indicators were plotted against existing economic data from past years in order to understand this relationship (Hobeika, 2019, Zreik, 2021). The hospitality and tourism industry suffered the most from massive turnovers¹ (Melkonian, 2020). Yet, this sector has great potential if cultural and natural resources were effectively valorized, an area that the Lebanese authorities have failed to utilize due to resource mismanagement (Knio & Bellos, 2018; Bellos, 2019).

Employee turnover has shown a relationship with economic crises across multiple industries, both in private and in the public sector (e.g., Baldwin, 1991; Babin & Boles, 1996; Adkins et al., 2001; Sousa-Poza, & Henneberger, 2004; Ismail et al., 2010; Battistelli et al., 2013; Wynen, & Op de Beeck, 2014). It was initially decided not to discuss employee turnover in the Lebanese Public Sector as it is beyond the scope of this study. Yet, small inferences on comparative natures will be made across different private and state firms. It is crucial to consider whether Lebanese Political Corruption brought about the economic crisis and whether it influences employee turnover in Lebanese public firms.

Turnover in the medical and other related sectors is related to job stability, job motivation, and several other environmental factors, including economic situations, which were evident in the 2019 Lebanese socio-economic crisis (Becker, 1978, Brannon et al., 2002; Sousa-Poza & Henneberger, 2004 and Kim, 2005; Buelens, & Van den Broeck, 2007; Galletta et al., 2011; Battistelli et al., 2013; Chaaban, 2019, Hobeika, 2019). We will investigate this further by studying the case of a university, a bank, and a firm in the hospitality and tourism sector in Lebanon (Hobeika, 2019). Moreover, we conducted several blind and confidential interviews targeting key decision-makers. Hence, results will be compared with existing literature (Stefaniak et al., 2012; Melkonian, 2020).

Aim and objectives

After the Lebanese people's anti-corruption revolution in October 2019, massive economic default indicators and their effects on turnovers were observed. This paper seeks to determine the causal relationship between them and employee turnover (Martin, 1979, Melkonian, 2020). Dr. Louis Hobeika, Economics Emeritus professor at Notre Dame University, recently studied the economic situation in Lebanon and presented at an economics seminar held at the Lebanese International University (LIU) Mount Lebanon Campus on October 9th, 2019, an overview of the situation (summarized in appendix 1). Similar arguments were also brought about by Dr. Jad Chaaban, an Economics professor at the American University of Beirut, since both mentioned that the situation was quasi-stable, even though the Lebanese Pound increasingly showed signs of imminent collapse (Chaaban, 2019; Hobeika, 2019).

Literature Review

Three previous studies confirmed that valorizing natural and cultural resources enhances economic development and improves tourism activities in Lebanon (Al-Sawi, 2018; Knio & Bellos, 2018; Bellos, 2019). However, the Lebanese authorities demonstrated management deficiencies that reinforced a dwindling economy, eventually leading to a dire

¹ For further reading, refer to www.libnanews.com and www.executive-magazine.com.lb.

socio-economic situation. COVID-19 and the Beirut Harbor Blast in August 2020 contributed to the failing economic crisis (El-Bacha, 2020a; Gerges, 2020). Moreover, El Bacha (2020a) believes that Lebanon is currently facing several economic problems due to the capital control exerted by the Lebanese banks and the coronavirus-related economic impediments. According to Rogoff (2020), economic crises were known to have severely impeded employee motivation and turnover.

Economic indicators

Economic indicators are summarized in the appendix for the last figures preceding the October 17th people's revolution, and appendix 1 shows actual values estimated by Hobeika (2019). They act as our Independent Variable (IV). These indicators were discussed based on the 2020 World Economic Forum.

Managerial decision-making

HR personnel is essential in preventing turnovers (Mondy, 2012). By keeping employees motivated, company managers reduce turnover and, at the same time, enhance productivity. This represents a second independent variable (IV) to measure workplace performance or productivity and assess job safety/satisfaction (Muchinsky & Morrow, 1980; Perumal et al., 2019; Melkonian, 2020). Figure 1 illustrates factors linked to job satisfaction and performance (Mondy, 2012). This is linked to career advancement, as it increases proportionally with job satisfaction.

Figure 1. Factors relating to job satisfaction and job performance (Mondy, 2012).

Recent studies show that as turnover rates increase, levels of employee motivation drop (Hellriegel & Slocum, 2007). This link was demonstrated in 2020 due to COVID-19. Blašková & Blaško (2011) studied managerial decision-making concerning turnovers and their effect on employee motivation. Employee participation in decision-making is viewed as a means of employee empowerment. Thus, decisions affecting employee motivation and other variables related to it, in turn, influence turnovers (Irawanto 2015; Ceschi 2017). This constitutes a useful parameter to estimate the impact of managerial decision-making on employee motivation. Previous studies demonstrated that if a company empowers its employees, it will boost their morale and enhance empowerment (Blašková et al. 2018). Such are the managerial decisions affected by COVID-19, as increasing job insecurities reduces employee motivation and satisfaction (Rogoff, 2020).

Reward management is one way to cater to employee empowerment (or motivation). This variable can enhance staff motivation and job satisfaction through cash bonuses (extrinsic) and employee noncash incentives (intrinsic). Both are linked to employee job satisfaction and decision-making processes, which are potential variables to consider (Brooks 2007; Zubair 2015). Employees can be empowered once they participate in companies' decision-making processes. Based on Figure 1, a proportional link with both variables can be inferred, as an increase in employee empowerment means an increase in employee motivation (Brooks 2007; Zubair 2015).

Motivation

Paillé (2013) discussed employee motivation through different phenomena observed in public sector institutions. Moreover, Lee and Raschke (2016) observed a positive relationship between employee motivation and work performance. Motivation has been an essential part of HRM practices. Studies on employee motivation include 'exploratory analyses of the role of motivation in the workplace (Hadziahmetovic et al., 2017), which is also affected by performance appraisals. This effect depends on the type of motivation and purpose of evaluations (Idowu, 2017). In this study, motivation acts as the moderating variable (MV).

Motivation can be enhanced through empowerment, especially in times of crisis (Devi, 2017; Youness, 2020). Career fulfillment was also linked to work motivation (Ayankola & Popoola, 2020). The more employees are motivated in the workplace, the better their job fulfillment will be associated with career fulfillment, self-esteem, and work motivation (Ayankola & Popoola 2020), a reason for linking it to career advancement in this study (Figure 1).

Employee motivation through measuring the effects of workplace incivility on job satisfaction has also been measured (Jamal 2020). Since this study has measured two variables inversely proportional to each other, an increase in one means a decrease in the other. Jamal (2020) measured the effect of workplace incivility on motivation and the relationship between decision-making and employee motivation, i.e., how a behavior change can be measured. Decision-making influences employees in multiple ways, and the most common ones are alterations in behavior after the decision has been passed (Pohanková, 2010). Figure 2 represents this link.

Figure 2. *Decision-making outcomes as influencing staff motivation (Pohanková, 2010).*

Edhund and Nilsson (2007) and Flynn (2013) believe that companies need to consider motivating employees to enhance productivity through various exploratory investigations. Kontakos (2017) proposed another way to study motivation by proposing circular economic systems (Figures 1 and 2). Thus, work motivation is to have well-motivated employees and managers who can motivate others (Edhund & Nilsson, 2007; Flynn, 2013; Kontakos, 2017). This can help in cases of pandemics such as COVID-19.

Intrinsic motivation, particularly in low-skilled work, is essential in such job settings. Intrinsic job quality, skill use, autonomy, and participative decision-making, are all linked to enchanting intrinsic employee motivation in such sectors (Janssen 2014). Nava (2014) believes in empowering women and treating women equally in the workplace to enhance motivation. If we go back to both Figures 1 and 2, we notice that employee motivation and satisfaction are almost directly related to each other, so making the right decisions as managers will allow employees to be more satisfied in their job, and de facto will be more

motivated at work (Maksic, 2016). This also shows a positive link with organizational performance. Hence, the impact of employees' motivation on organizational effectiveness is proportional (Nguyen 2017). This is linked to strategic human resource management and organizational performance, whereby making the right decisions enhances company productivity (Nemli-Çalışkan 2010; Khosorowshahi & Nejad, 2014; Wheelen et al., 2014; Peregrino de Brito & Barbosa de Oliveira, 2016). This is relevant as well for the COVID-19 pandemic lockdown period.

Turnover

In this study, turnover is considered the dependent variable (DV). Sousa-Poza and Henneberger (2004) studied the phenomenon of job mobility in turnover studies by analyzing the role of both variables in relation to each other. They noticed that turnover intention reflects an individual's conscious and deliberate willfulness to quit one's job or organization within a certain period, which could pose a significant problem in the healthcare system resulting in a high turnover rate (Sousa-Poza & Henneberger, 2004). The impact of strategic human resource management on organizational performance, a phenomenon linked to turnovers, can be helpful in conditions such as COVID-19 (Kauffman et al., 1996; Nemli-Çalışkan 2010; Khosorowshahi & Nejad, 2014; Peregrino de Brito & Barbosa de Oliveira 2016). However, the study of managerial decision-making, employee motivation, job satisfaction, human capital, competitive advantage, and strategic human resources management are all linked to estimating turnover rates. Yet, this is not often possible to estimate in times of crisis (Kauffmann et al., 1996; Wheelen et al., 2014; Rogoff, 2020).

Two cases of turnovers in two countries will be discussed (Lebanon, a developing country, and France, a developed country). Both were compelled to be on state-enforced mandatory lockdown for three months in Mid-2020 (El-Bacha, 2020a). The cases illustrate how each country responded to this pandemic. In the case of Lebanon, the currency dropped from 1500 – 3000 LBP to the USD to a staggering 8000 – 10000 LBP to USD due to the hardships impeded by both political corruption and the Coronavirus (El-Bacha, 2020). As Gerges (2020) pointed out, on August 4th, 2020, at roughly 6:00 pm local time, a massive explosion destroyed the Beirut Harbor and annihilated half of Lebanon's capital city. The damages were estimated to reach between 10 to 15 billion USD.

During the last four decades, 300 billion USD were stolen from the Lebanese public and private funds since our economy was mostly a rentier economy and axed on imports, making the Lebanese Society a dependent society on imported goods (85-90% of goods were imported once there were US dollars in the BDL treasuries). Zreik (2021) pointed out that we should shift to agrarian, industrial and local production economies. Yet, she discusses illegal transactions, such as money laundering, which prevent the Lebanese economy from recovering. Moreover, corruption and terrorism turned out to be major impediments in this shift from a rentier economy to a production one (Zreik 2021). This may explain why the defaulting economy enhances turnover, as turnovers increase once the economy deteriorates further.

In Lebanon, the debt-to-GDP ratio dropped from 152% to nearly 172%. Unemployment soared to 50% (with roughly 2,000,000 people jobless), and poverty levels increased, with 22% of the Lebanese population being extremely poor and 53% being poor (www.executive-magazine.com.lb). The inequitable wealth distribution is 70% of all assets belonging to 1% of the population, and the remaining 30% is spread among 99% of the people (www.libnanews.com). The Hospitality and Tourism sector got severely affected, with several restaurants and Hotels ceasing their operations. Notable examples are the iconic

"Hotel le Bristol" and "Coca-Cola Lebanon," among others (see: www.libnanews.com). As such, it was nearly impossible to revamp Lebanese businesses. The chosen cases in Lebanon are the Al Habtoor Hotel, which was entirely shut down, and the American University of Beirut Medical Center (AUBMC), which had to downsize (Azzi, 2020; Zaazaa, 2020). Table 1 shows the massive firings from June 2020 from the American University of Beirut (AUB) and July 2020 from AUBMC, totaling 50% of their total staff. The data did not separate AUB from AUBMC employees, but it is assumed that the faculty were considered AUB academics.

France, on the other hand, unlike Lebanon, had a high contamination case level concerning COVID-19. Roughly 25% of the country (Nord, pas de Calais, le Grand Est, and so on) have had the highest peaks. As such, the country could subsidize some or most of the companies on its soil with the 600 billion Euros bailout money, which helped prevent bankruptcy.

Table 1. *Collective staff before and after the massive sackings at AUB and AUBMC.*

Academic staff	1,200
Administrative staff	4,340
Fired staff (June 2020)	1500
Fired staff at AUBMC (July 2020)	850

In contrast to Lebanon, France was one of the EU countries that had part of the 600 billion Euros to revamp its economies. The state had helped the industries recoup again in case of cessation of activities associated with the COVID-19 lockdown. So, in essence, it was easier for the residents of France to revamp their activities in the country and consider alternatives for mass firings (Figure 3).

Figure 3. *An alternative to massive sackings can be utilized in times of crisis (Beam, 2014).*

The best performing staff are graded as "A" and the worst as "C". Suppose we exclude the origin (i.e., the point of junction of the abscissa and ordinate). Thus, based on performance evaluations for underperformed employees, companies will fire the poorly performing employees before firing the good ones. Experts agree that the best-performing employees must be fairly treated and kept at all costs, especially in times of crisis (Mondy,

2012; Beam, 2014).

In general, when linking corporate HR decisions with boosting employee morale, typically, the decisions do not promote mass sackings (Lambert, & Hogan, 2009). Severe massive layoffs happened due to the COVID-19 pandemic, and in Lebanon, several companies like Coca-Cola, LeMall Habtoor, and Le Bristol ceased their operations due to the socio-economic situation (Azzi, 2020; Rogoff, 2020; Zaazaa, 2020).

Staff motivation in such cases has been negatively affected. Thus, employee motivation, job safety, and satisfaction will suffer when companies choose not to prioritize them regardless of the situation. According to Carsten and Spector (1987), Rogoff (2020), and Zaazaa (2020), institutions will lose their employee motivation if they decide not to favor employees' well-being. Consequently, employees' productivity will drop.

This seems to have been the case at institutions such as AUBMC (Azzi, 2020; Zaazaa, 2020). Rogoff (2020) presented other COVID-19 unemployment-related issues that also seemed to have hampered employees' motivation. At AUBMC, 2,350 employees were terminated in 2 months (Table 1). Likewise, other sectors of operation suffered from the COVID-19 pandemic (Azzi, 2020; Zaazaa, 2020).

Beam (2014) discussed the parameters used in the survey question that 'the respondents' companies had/used steps to prevent turnover' and clearly stated that most of the respondents disagreed with the above statement. In other words, most companies do not apply or do not enforce turnover policies. Azzi (2020) and Zaazaa (2020) agree with this as when the 2350 staff were fired from AUB and AUBMC. The upper management decided to massively fire them without prior notice, indicating the absence of layoff policies or their application.

Hence, authors such as Azzi (2020) and Zaazaa (2020), among others, assumed that not all firms prevented turnover in Lebanon, and some encouraged it. Based on Lambert and Hogan (2009), this shows to be a significant hindrance in enhancing employee motivation since, in such cases, managerial decisions are geared towards cost reduction irrespective of employees' demotivation for fear of getting laid off. Moreover, Melkonian (2020) argued that most Lebanese companies across various sectors do not have a turnover policy. The situation is tricky and may pause legal concerns (Greenhalgh & Rosenblatt, 1984; Al-Khatib & Abdallah, 2017; Majzoub, 2018).

Lambert and Hogan (2009) demonstrate that the companies that do prevent turnover actually enhance employee morale. However, "goodwill" is one of the ways to keep employees satisfied and not voluntarily terminate their jobs. Moreover, companies can practice good organizational behavior skills, which can reflect on employee workplace behavior as in change in motivation, positively or negatively (Robbins & Judge, 2012). Companies can also help their employees (or not) in coping with anxiety and mental health issues (Wickramasinghe & Perera, 2012).

Ultimately, the decisions that facilitate massive sackings will seriously hinder motivation. The termination cases observed in Lebanon are worth investigating, noting that during COVID-19, the discharging cases were evident worldwide (Azzi, 2020; Zaazaa, 2020; Rogoff, 2020).

Methodology

Based on Saunders et al. (2019), we decided to design a survey, which was used to gather data about the stakeholders' attitudes through semi-structured questionnaires as our data collection method for the pilot study (Saunders et al., 2019). Those questions were addressed on Survey Monkey. We then interviewed key people in three institutions to pursue further the investigation, utilizing mixed qualitative (interview) and quantitative (questionnaire) methods (for the methods used, see: Saunders et al., 2019).

A Cronbach's alpha statistical analysis followed this to verify the validity and accuracy of our data (where initial values of about 0.23 mean that the dataset is weakly correlated). After splitting the data, we got 0.86 (which indicates a good correlation). We selected excel (for running the Cronbach Alpha test) because the study was preliminary, as a future quantitative study will still be conducted to effectively examine the impact of the Lebanese Economic crisis on employee turnover through employee motivation (Saunders et al., 2019). Finally, we present the research design scheme by concluding the chapter with the research method selected.

Findings

Pilot Study (Survey Monkey)

We defined our variables based on the preliminary findings of the pilot study. In general, over 70% of the respondents agree that the economic crisis causes turnover, and only 30% do not. Twenty-two respondents answered at the initial data collection stage during the last week of January 2020 till the end of the first three weeks of February 2020. In further research that aims to target a larger sample, we expect to see a variation in responses. For this research, Creswell and Creswell (2018) were referenced as the used methodology since they explain the mixed methods applied in this research.

Interviews

Six key people were interviewed across the three sectors of education, banking, and tourism. In theory, these three sectors can generate economic growth in Lebanon. The decision-makers targeted from each sector were considered top decision-makers in their company. We interviewed the campus and academic director for a higher education institution in the north-eastern outskirts of Beirut, a branch manager and his bank assistant, and decision-makers from representative hospitality and tourism firms in Beirut. Stefaniak et al. (2012) and Saunders et al. (2019) were relied upon for our methodology.

The interviewee responses matched the pilot study results and the literature review findings per their respective sectors. Banks seem not to show high turnover but can have employee demotivation once the socio-economic situation, affecting all tiers of Lebanese Society, adds to the tension caused by angry customers or undesirable work conditions. Both interviewed bank managers notified us that at that particular branch, the environment is such that employee morale is boosted even though their central HR department does not have turnover policies per se. However, it is up to the individual managers to ensure an environment that favors employee productivity (tied to sales turnover) and that motivation is enhanced or decreased by stressing the work environment (Wickramasinghe & Perera, 2012).

Nevertheless, the higher education school we targeted had problems paying some of its employees on time or had been paying reduced wages during the current crisis. However,

employee motivation was mildly affected, and no massive employee turnover occurred (unlike in other sectors that dramatically suffered from this crunch). The measured effects should be adequately triangulated to the literature review as previous studies, showing similar findings that correlate well with the results we are gathering here. This triangulation is illustrated in figure 4.

Figure 4. *The concept of triangulation for comparing data (Saunders et al., 2019).*

Both decision-makers from the educational institution agree that, as the environment is friendly, it nurtures a setting in which its staff members feel a sense of belonging. Both interviewees concur that concerns are brought up in extreme economic situations, but as a family, it always unites together to resolve any upcoming issue through dialogue (Lee & Hong, 2011). During the COVID-19 period and the dire economic situation, the administration advises their employees to be more lenient toward their lifestyle to prepare themselves for the worst. So, the best solution is to keep a positive attitude toward life, and their issues (no matter how small or large) will look minimal and, therefore, will be easier to solve (Lee, & Hong, 2011).

At the same time, the leaders are helping employees boost their motivation (or morale) to keep performing optimally by nurturing a positive environment. Therefore, by doing so, they will ensure that their jobs are safe. Both interviewees at the academic institution confirmed that there is no turnover (both by staff and students) as the institute strives for excellence. For them, the best quality people can have is to stay connected with real life. At the same time, employees and administration need to stay focused on the goals (and objectives) by always keeping a positive mind will ultimately make them reach their full potential (Hatun, 2010).

So, in a way as to conclude, according to the institution's decision-makers, the goodwill is always there, regardless of the situation. However, in some cases, and reciting the above point, people are advised to stay conservative in issues regarding expenditures. We understand from their answers that the institution suffered no real setbacks in paying their staff on time, and we read between the lines that both leaders concurred on the fact that their institution does its best to boost employee morale and praises "best practices" to say that there was nearly no measurable "or massive" turnover.

In the target sample of the hospitality sector, we had a difficult time targeting the right institution to measure how badly this sector was affected. Since we found out that the majority of the surveyed population feels turnover is massively caused by the disastrous economic crunch (chiefly induced by the corruption of the Lebanese Political Elite and mismanagement of state and public funds) across industries, businesses were shutting down. Since we decided to target both tourism (previously defined both in terms of managing cultural and natural resources) and hospitality (as the part covering hotels and restaurants), we need to understand how this industry work in order properly profile potential tourist profiles that were previously sketched out in previous studies in this sector.

To date, Lebanon targets European tourists with cultural tours, museums, festivals

(like Ehdeniyat, "Festival de Baalbeck," Festival de Beiteddine," etc.), concerts, and other cultural activities to boost the Lebanese Culture. Lebanon targets as well Asian tourists with expensive hotels and luxury resorts. According to Bellos (2019), the Lebanese authorities are ignoring the profiling of Cultural tourists and focusing primarily on the Luxury resort segments that generate economic revenues.

With this in mind, advocates of cultural and natural tourism are faced with highly corrupt institutions, which do not hesitate to destroy natural resources and cultural heritage to produce resorts and illegally trespass on public grounds (citing various articles on www.libnannews.com and other journals bringing about the highly corrupt construction sector). Today, this sector, according to the testimonials we got, was hit very hard since we are close to a chaotic situation with the fraudulent activities between the Central Bank, close to 95% of the banks, the corrupt political elite, and the shortage in essential commodities (like US dollars, gasoline, basic food sources, and medications).

As a result, not many tourists would want to visit a country facing such economic downturns. So, massive closings of restaurants and other hospitality services are expected (see: www.libannews.com). So, we gather that this industry as a whole is aggressive, shows no solution to turnover, and does not care about employee demotivation, massive turnover, or even outcomes of anxiety and depression, as the testimonials were collected (this is induced by the harsh construction industry, SOLIDERE, the CDR or urban development facilitator). Typically, any institution that boosts our morale always cares for its staff irrespective of the economic situation (Lambert & Hogan, 2009). Moreover, the Lebanese government turned a blind eye and showed carelessness toward this practice (see: www.libannews.com).

To sum up, both interviews from this sector were categorical; there is a deficient sense of the family environment, and does not intend to unite to resolve upcoming issues (Maertz et al., 2007; Lee & Hong, 2011). Despite this terrible socio-economic state, the key decision-makers in this industry do not care about advising their people to be more conservative in their lifestyles or to provide them with safety and security. As such, this industry has no solution to boost employee morale or pay their employees' salaries on time (Greenhalgh & Rosenblatt, 1984).

The following section is a recollection of expert testimonials from various field experts. Therefore, even though the best solution is to keep a positive attitude toward life and, as such, minimize all hardships felt by their collaborators. Had these institutions developed such preventive measures, there would not have been such a massive turnover. Since there was no turnover policy at all and many operations in this industry were unethical and illegal, there was no way that such crises would look minimal and, as a result, would be very difficult to resolve.

The first question the interviewees addressed in the Tourism and Hospitality sector is preventive and focuses on avoiding or preventing turnover, and the answer revealed that the industry shows no preventative measure whatsoever.

The second question was also replied along the same line, as no measures were taken to prevent employee dissatisfaction and demotivation. Therefore, the leaders from the institutions we sampled preemptively targeted the anxiety and depression issue (Lambert & Hogan, 2009).

The third question proved to us that there is no existing turnover policy. Whereas the fourth question showed us the lack of goodwill in this industry. Finally, the fifth question

revealed that this industry lacked organizational behavior skills (Noaman, 2018).

Structured Surveys

To date, 22 respondents answered the Survey Monkey questions disseminated from November 2019 to February 2020 at the institution where the initial research was carried out. Following the research, the next step was to numerically test the theory of "Economic crises like the Lebanese one will lead to turnover or not" (Chaaban, 2008; Saunders et al., 2019). Through the Cronbach Alpha Test, we determined that questions 2 to question 8 are internally correlated, as shown in Table 2.

Table 2: Correlated Results.

Cronbach's Alpha	0.864937281
Split-Half (odd-even) Correlation	0.989127985
Split-Half with Spearman-Brown Adjustment	0.994534281
Mean for Test	1.40004
Standard Deviation for Test	0.735917872
KR21 (use only 0 and 1 to enter data for this)	-1.35910907
KR20 (use only 0 and 1 to enter data for this)	-1.1867624

Questions 1, 9, and 10 turned out to be moderately correlated (Table 3). It is important to reflect on that point while data interpretation is carried out. These questions can be surveyed independently, grouped, or reformulated. For the time being, the focus needs to be on the collected data and comparing it with past data (see: <https://tradingeconomics.com>).

The Cronbach Alpha results required more work on the results such that, through Tables 2 and 3, we can show the best way to correlate the data to reach both valid and reliable outcomes that can be utilized for further research (Figure 2).

Table 3: Moderately correlated results.

Cronbach's Alpha	0.66519435
Split-Half (odd-even) Correlation	0.881719817
Split-Half with Spearman-Brown Adjustment	0.937142511
Mean for Test	0.6
Standard Deviation for Test	0.524902669
KR21 (use only 0 and 1 to enter data for this)	-1.16335271
KR20 (use only 0 and 1 to enter data for this)	-0.82460278

Results and Discussion

The first set of questions from Survey Monkey

These match with question one from the unstructured interview. So, a comparison will be made on this basis following the mixed qualitative-quantitative research method hinted out by Saunders et al. (2019) for data collection:

Question 1 from the Survey Monkey questions stating that "with the terrible economic situation in Lebanon now, massive employee turnovers have occurred across multiple sectors" demonstrates fascinating outcomes. Since we generally noticed that 90.91% accept the concept (Mobley et al., 1979; Dalessio et al., 1986). The Lebanese case is no different from the significant crises the rest of the world has witnessed. Major economic crunches like the 1929 Great Depression showed massive layoffs and all other economic troughs. Yet, COVID-19 saw unprecedented crises (Melkonian, 2020). The remaining 9.09% of the respondents who

were asked the questions showed a neutral stance. Perhaps the 9.09% of the sampled population (we sampled people across sectors) who were indifferent or neutral were not affected by the 2019 Economic Depression, which worsened due to COVID-19.

Conversely, the 90.91% of the population who said massive turnovers occur in economic crises are pretty right. Unfortunately, once one ignores the neutral responses, 100% of the responders agree. This sadly makes sense (Lambert, & Hogan, 2009).

Question 2 from the Survey Monkey questions stating that "your company has preventive measures against employee turnover," also shows interesting findings. Overall, 13.64% of the respondents agree with the above statement. Nevertheless, generally, 31.82% of the respondents disagree. Yet, with COVID-19, this worsened in many sectors, and there were mass turnovers (Melkonian, 2020). Irrespective of the remaining 54.55% of the population who showed a neutral stance, clearly around 70% of the population showing a stance disagreed with that statement, whereas only 30% of that sample agreed. This indicates that most respondents were against the statement, again stressing that most of the sampled population believe that their companies do not have preventive measures against turnover (Youness, 2020).

To recap, the bank manager we interviewed (using instructed surveying techniques) confirmed that the banking industry generally does not face severe turnover and that it, based on each branch manager, is based on how effective the preventive measures are against turnover. Melkonian (In Press) shows that due to COVID-19, this worsened. As the Survey shows, the other sectors demonstrate different turnover detection or prevention patterns (whether in the educational, hospitality, medical, state, or any other industry). Statistically, turnover was seen across many sectors; some were more hard-hit than others.

The second set of questions from Survey Monkey

The following questions from the survey match with question two from the interview.

Question 3 from the Survey Monkey questions stating that "Knowing that in this case, high employee turnover occurs does your company help its staff in boosting their motivation (or morale) to keep performing optimally?" displays precise results as well (Meier & Hicklin, 2008). As a result, 27.28% of respondents agree with the above statement. However, 40.91% of the population disagrees with the statement. So, if we ignore the 31.82% of the population that is neutral about the statement, we effectively come up with 40% of the respondents taking an actual stance to agree with this statement, and the remaining 60% disagree. Melkonian (2020) agrees with the above. According to the literature review and statistics, more than half of the respondents disagreed with the above statement. This agrees with current cases under COVID-19.

Question 4 from the Survey Monkey questions states that "once employees get demotivated from current work conditions imposed by the crisis in Lebanon since Summer 2019 (e.g., poor pay, less salary, more hours, etc.) or quit/terminate their job, your company has concrete steps in place to prevent this turnover to happen" shows interesting findings as well. So, 13.64% agree with this statement, and 45.46% disagree. Irrespective of the 40.91% of the population who seems indifferent, the sample of the respondents taking a stance disagrees at 76%, whereas only 24% agree. Thus, most respondents disagree, as companies generally do not boost their employees' morale, which is wrong! Melkonian (2020) agrees as well.

The third set of questions from Survey Monkey

The following questions from the survey match with question three from the interview.

Question 5 from the Survey Monkey questions states, "Supposing the company has a network to prevent turnover from happening, you believe that your company has or implements "a turnover policy" effectively," also interesting findings. So, 9.09% of the population agrees, whereas 45.46% disagrees. Furthermore, if we ignore the 45.45% of the population who kept a neutral stance, we see 18% agreeing and 82% disagreeing. Melkonian (2020) agrees as well. This demonstrates that most firms do not follow an effective turnover prevention policy, or if they have one, it is ineffective! Melkonian (2020) agrees.

Question 6, "Your company shows goodwill to its employees (Examples of goodwill are: increasing the benefits, paying salaries on time and in full, etc.)," also shows interesting findings. Only 31.82% of the respondents agreed with the above statement, whereas 22.73% of the population was neutral, and the remaining 45.45% of the surveyed population disagreed. Melkonian (2020) agrees as well. Ignoring the neutral responses, we notice that 42% of our respondents accepted the above statement, and 58% rejected it (we consider that less than half of our respondents disagreed with that statement about goodwill). The above result is confirmed by Melkonian (2020), as mass turnovers have occurred in firms showing no goodwill at all, and sadly, this is the case in Lebanon.

The fourth set of questions from Survey Monkey

The following questions from the survey match with question four from the interview.

Question 7, "In case the current economic situation has caused anxiety and depression among employees in your company, its HR department has concrete steps to help them cope better with this," clearly states the relationship. The findings were interesting (Lambert & Hogan, 2009). For the following statement, 18.18% of the respondents agree with it. Yet, 27.27% are neutral, and 54.55% of the respondents disagree. If we disregard neutral answers, we get 33 % of the respondents agreeing with the above statement and 67% disagreeing (Melkonian, 2020). Nevertheless, 75% of the respondents disagree with the above statement, whereby most institutions in Lebanon do not have HR departments doing their jobs as per the sampled population. In other words, anxiety and depression may increase, as only 25% agree with the statement (Wickramasinghe & Perera, 2012, Melkonian, 2020).

Question 8, "Your company has good organizational behavior skills in the case at hand," yielded good results. We noticed that 27.27% of the population agrees with the above statement. 18.18% of the population show a neutral stance as per the statement, whereas 54.55% disagree. Ignoring the neutral, 33% of the respondents agreed with the above statement. The remaining 67% of companies do not show good organizational behavior skills (Wickramasinghe & Perera, 2012; Youness, 2020).

The fifth set of questions from Survey Monkey

The last set of the Survey monkey questionnaire does not reflect on answers from the interviews and will be used as a conclusion for the surveying process in the sectors we were able to sample. This set of questions seems to be poorly correlated, as including them in the dataset by some respondents could lead to erratic data. Therefore, this needs to be tested using Cronbach's Alpha Test (Saunders et al., 2019).

Question 9, "Turnover hinders motivation, productivity, revenue, and organization performance," is important and answered correctly. 84% of our respondents agreed with the above statement. Only, according to the 16% who rejected this statement, turnover does not

hinder them (Mobley et al., 1979; Cotton & Tuttle, 1986; Carson et al., 1994; Dalessio et al., 1986; Meier & Hicklin, 2008; Melkonian, 2020). Bellos's work mentions that turnover is very high in Archeology, as there are virtually no opportunities for degree holders in this field (Bellos, 2019; Melkonian, 2020).

Question 10, "Massive employee turnover harms, rather than help, institutions irrespective of the bad economic situation," was answered (Martin, 1979). We noticed that 72.73% of the respondents agreed with the statement, whereas 27.27% were neutral. This makes sense, as turnover indeed does hinder indentations because if we ignore the neutral answers, we have a 100% agreement with the above statement (Melkonian, 2020). Table 4, showing existing and past economics, and forecasted data, is presented for comparison with current statistics (Hobeika, 2019).

Conclusions and Recommendations

The contribution to knowledge, literature, originality, and practitioners is listed as follows: First, the Lebanese October 2019 anti-corruption revolution clarified that nepotism is pervasive across all sectors and that COVID-19 accentuated it (Hobeika, 2019; Melkonian, 2020). Second, after identifying that the root cause of the Lebanese Economic Crisis was the above-mentioned political corruption, we can state that it is one of the main causes of demotivation and turnover, yet it differs among researchers (Melkonian, 2020; Youness, 2020). Third, thorough Economics studies are lacking in this country, so it is important to link them to turnover studies in the future (Trad, 2018; Melkonian, 2020). Fourth, the outcome of the 2019 Lebanese October 17th Revolution has raised awareness of the corrupted political elite and how it was running the show and monopolizing the country's resources, even so-called development projects (Youness, 2020).

As shown by all respondents, 100% agree that with Lebanon's terrible economic situation, massive employee turnovers have occurred across multiple sectors. They also agree that massive employee turnover harms, rather than help, institutions irrespective of the dire economic situation. Entrepreneurship is the solution and needs consideration (Trad, 2018). Nevertheless, the majority (68.18%) believe that turnover hinders motivation, productivity, revenue, and organizational performance, and 18.18% of them are neutral. However, 13.64% of the sampled population did not believe that massive turnover hampers the economy, defeats employee motivation, and leads to poorer performance (Meier & Hicklin, 2008; Melkonian, 2020).

So, we could see a relationship between HR decisions and employee motivation. This includes details on how companies deal with panic situations, as, at times, company managers need to treat these concerns immediately to make employees feel safe and secure in their jobs. This highly depends on boosting employee morale to optimize performance despite the COVID-19-induced economic crisis (Rogoff, 2020). The reverse was shown with other institutions, such as AUBMC, as panic seemed high and resulted in many employees' immediate notice of job termination (Azzi, 2020; Zaazaa, 2020).

Regarding limitations, COVID-19 lockdowns were the major setback when the research was initially conducted. In future studies, it is suggested to delve more into the economic situation, mainly because it has been changing rapidly in the last few years. Studies with objectives of finding solutions to limit attritions, turnovers, or massive layoffs as more Lebanese businesses collapse, can also stem from this study's outcomes. The public sector, the private sector, and the academic body could present solutions. Moreover, future research

can test whether a Helix approach can be applied in Lebanon and which form. This will result from industry, academia, and government collaboration. As the industry informs academia of its needs, the government proposes the policies and structures to make this approach successful.

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Appendix 1: Lebanon's selected economic indicators 2016-23

	2016			Proj.				
	Act.	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022	2023
Output and prices								
(Annual percentage change)								
Real GDP (market prices)	1.0	1.2	1.5	1.8	2.2	2.6	2.9	2.9
GDP deflator	-0.7	2.5	2.7	3.3	2.4	2.3	2.1	2.1
Consumer prices (end-of-period)	3.1	5.0	3.5	2.5	2.5	2.5	2.5	2.5
Consumer prices (period average)	-0.8	4.5	4.3	3.0	2.5	2.5	2.5	2.5
Investment and saving								
(In percent of GDP)								
Gross capital formation	20.4	22.7	21.4	20.4	19.4	18.4	18.4	17.8
Government	1.4	1.4	1.4	1.4	1.4	1.4	1.4	1.4
Nongovernment	19.0	21.3	20.0	18.9	18.0	17.0	17.0	16.4
Gross national savings	-2.1	-2.2	-4.3	-4.8	-5.2	-5.8	-5.3	-5.5
Government	-7.7	-5.9	-9.1	-9.6	-9.9	-10.3	-11.0	-11.6
Nongovernment	5.6	3.6	4.8	4.8	4.6	4.5	5.7	6.1
Central government finances (cash basis)								
(In percent of GDP)								
Revenue (including grants)	20.0	22.1	23.0	23.2	23.3	23.1	23.0	23.0
Expenditure	29.2	29.4	33.6	34.2	34.6	34.9	35.4	36.0
Budget balance (including grants)	-9.2	-7.3	-10.6	-11.0	-11.3	-11.7	-12.4	-13.0
Primary balance (including grants)	0.1	2.5	0.2	0.3	0.5	0.4	0.3	0.3
Total government debt	151	153	157	161 ⁶	165 ⁶	169	173	178
(Annual percentage change, unless otherwise indicated)								
Monetary sector								
Credit to the private sector	6.1	6.1	4.2	5.1	4.7	4.9	5.0	5.0
Reserve money	27.7	32.0	-11.5	2.2	2.2	2.2	2.1	2.0
Broad money ²	7.6	4.1	5.0	5.0	5.0	5.0	5.0	5.0
Deposit dollarization (level)	65.9	68.8	69.0	69.0	69.0	69.0	69.0	69.0
Interest rates (period average, in percent)								
Three-month treasury bill yield	4.4	5.1	5.8	6.1	6.2	6.3	6.4	6.4
Five-year treasury bill yield	6.8	7.9	8.2	8.4	8.5	8.6	8.7	n.a.
External sector								
(In percent of GDP, unless otherwise indicated)								
Exports of goods and services (in US\$, percentage change)	-4.5	2.6	6.0	5.2	5.3	5.2	5.5	5.6
Imports of goods and services (in US\$, percentage change)	0.4	6.9	7.0	3.0	3.1	4.0	4.3	4.4
Balance of goods and services	-24.0	-26.3	-27.4	-26.1	-24.9	-24.2	-23.6	-23.0
Current account	-22.5	-25.0	-25.8	-25.2	-24.7	-24.2	-23.7	-23.3
Foreign direct investment	4.0	4.6	4.0	4.0	4.0	4.0	4.0	4.0
Total external debt ³	190	198	202	205	208	211	213	216
Gross reserves (in billions of U.S. dollars) ⁴	40.2	40.6	37.5	33.7	29.9	26.1	22.4	18.6
In months of next year imports of goods and services	14.7	13.9	12.4	10.8	9.2	7.7	6.3	5.1
In percent of short-term external debt ⁵	48.0	44.8	38.8	32.7	27.3	22.4	18.1	14.1
In percent of banking system foreign currency deposits	37.6	35.1	30.7	26.2	22.2	18.4	15.0	11.9
In percent of total banking system deposits	24.8	24.1	21.2	18.1	15.3	12.7	10.4	8.2
Memorandum items:								
Nominal GDP (in billions of U.S. dollars)	49.6	51.5	53.6	56.4	59.0	61.9	65.0	68.3
Non-resident deposits (staff estimate, percent change)	11.7	3.8	5.0	5.0	5.0	5.0	5.0	5.0
Commercial bank total assets (percent of GDP)	394	396	394	394	392	389	385	n.a.

²Defined as currency in circulation plus resident and nonresident deposits.

³Includes nonresident deposits.

⁴Excluding gold and encumbered assets.

⁵Short-term debt on a remaining maturity basis, including short-term nonresident deposits.

Note. Actual figures for 2019 were close to the projected culminating between 160 to 170%. Under COVID-19, this value nearly doubled from its initial estimate in March 2020; by December, the value nearly tripled.

(Source: Hobeika, 2019).

Appendix 2: Economic indicators

The following eleven economic indicators were raised at the 2020 Davos Economic Forum:

A.1 First Indicator

The Tourism Sector as a way to prevent Economic Collapse (indicator selected since tourism is one of Lebanon's best industries), pre-COVID-19: It is a worldwide known fact that economic development and enhancing tourism activities show a causal relationship that needs

to be tested. In Lebanon, unlike other cities, Sidon and Jbeil proved to have yielded monumental archeology capable of attracting certain types of tourists, mainly Europeans (Bellos, 2019). Moreover, Tyre and Byblos, to a certain extent, were able to preserve their heritage for tourism purposes. Recent figures of the tourism sector incurring worldwide losses caused by COVID-19 in the order of 900 bn USD were presented.

However, he demonstrated that Beirut, due to political corruption or voluntary plans from CDR (or SOLIDERE) or the decision-makers, ignored the preservation of our heritage and was destroyed at the expense of illegal and anarchic urbanization (Bellos, 2019). A case was with the loss of a unique Ancient Phoenician vestige case that occurred on June 27th, 2012, when the late Minister of Culture, H.E. Gaby Layyoun, voted in favor of the destruction of BEY 194 (the Vth Cent. BC Persian harbor structure) instead of preserving it. That alone could have benefitted tourism and, as a result, could have increased the number of incoming tourists to the ancient Mediterranean Harbors (Bellos, 2019).

A.2. Second Indicator

The Banking Sector, as a second Economic indicator: We are examining this issue in terms of corruption. Furthermore, we will raise the issues of Capital control and Haircut. Several bank managers we asked confirmed that "haircuts" will not be applied yet (Al-Khatib & Abdallah, 2017) and that this will only be applied to accounts over 300,000 USD. At the same time, they notified us that 50,000 USD is the maximum limit in case of bank default. If the sector collapses completely, the 1st 50,000 USD will be insured (see: www.dailystar.com.lb). The following studies, yielding similar arguments, will aid us in comprehending this issue better (Chaaban, 2007; 2008; Salti & Chaaban, 2012; Salti et al., 2013; Hobeika, 2019).

A.3. Third Indicator

Overview of the Lebanese Economic Indicators, as hinted out by the Davos WEF (as presented on: <https://tradingeconomics.com/lebanon/indicators>). Farnham (2015) defines these indicators individually in his book treating on "Economics for Managers." We will briefly hint out that all these macroeconomic indicators are to be taken seriously if we want to see where we are heading in the next three years and if there is a way out of this crisis, or at least to understand the root causes of why we are so poorly rated by Standards & Poor, and Moody's Criteria (see: www.libnanews.com). So, we define, in brief, the following macroeconomic indicators in overview form (as taken from <https://tradingeconomics.com>). So, the economic indicators for Lebanon encompass actual values, historical information, an economic calendar, time-series statistics, business news, long-term forecasts, and short-term predictions for our economy. Here are the indicators:

1. LBP Currency: Daily average estimate: 1506 LBP to the USD (we listed the official rate from the Lebanese Central Bank as estimated now in February 2020). Note: we disregarded the illegal, fraudulent rate the market exerts to play on the corruption-controlled rate of 2000 – 2500 LBP to the USD to bring awareness to the Lebanese political leaders. The consumer dictates the market, not those sitting in their ivory towers!
2. Stock Market (points): 619 points (February 2020).
3. GDP Annual Growth Rate (%): 1% annual growth rate (last estimated: December 2018).
4. Unemployment Rate (%): 6.2% (last estimated: December 2019).
5. Inflation Rate (%): 6.96% (last estimate: December 2019).
6. Interest Rate (%): 6.75% (February 2020).

7. Balance of Trade (USD Million): -972 Million USD (last estimated: November 2019).
8. Current Account (USD Million): 1143 million USD (last estimated: November 2019).
9. Current Account to GDP (%): -27% (last estimated: December 2018).
10. Government Debt to GDP (%): 152% (last estimated: December 2018).²
11. Government Budget (% of GDP): -11% (last estimated: December 2018).
12. Corporate Tax Rate (%): 17% (last estimated December 2019).
13. Personal Income Tax Rate (%): 24% (last estimated: December 2019).

Here are some other indicators on GDP (as per <http://documents.worldbank.org>):

1. Percent Deficit of Electricité du Liban to GDP: 11.5% (estimated in 2018).
2. Percent of total revenue dedicated to paying State Employee wages: 46% (estimated in 2018).
3. Percent dedicated to State interest payments: 32% (Estimated in 2018)

A.4. Fourth Indicator: GDP²

We selected GDP as an economic health indicator, but we will provide some information about why our Debt to GDP ratio (152%) is so catastrophically high. We will also present factual figures about the Lebanese political corruption causing the high public debt and illustrate the economic collapse through documented sources. Farnham (2015) estimates how economists calculate GDP and how this is applied to Lebanon. In this part, we will not define this as irrelevant, but we want to clarify this issue to our corrupt politicians. Lebanon is one of the only countries worldwide whose GNP is 100 times higher than our GDP. We now know why.

Here, we listed the following about GDP as per the last annual estimate:

1. GDP (USD Billion): 56.64 billion USD (last estimate: December 2018).
2. GDP Constant Prices (LBP Billion): 64,162 billion LBP (last estimate: December 2018). The USD equivalent is: 42.78 billion USD.
3. GDP per capita (USD): 6250 USD (last estimate: December 2018).
4. GDP per capita PPP (USD) 11607 USD (last estimate: December 2018).
5. Gross Fixed Capital Formation (LBP Billion) 16,174 billion LBP (last estimate: December 2018). The USD equivalent is: 10.78 billion USD.

A.5. Fifth Indicator: Labor²

This will show the recent high unemployment rates as an indicator of economic collapse (Farnham, 2015). defines that the active labor force is not the same as the entire population, as it disregards the non-institutionalized population (underage children, teenagers, civil society workers, state employees and elderly (retired people), and elders residing in retirement homes, or seeking very high medical bills (Farnham, 2015). In the institutionalized population, the labor force is the available workforce that can be employed. It is generally used to describe those working for a single company or industry but can also apply to a geographic region like a city, state, or country (Farnham, 2015).

Within a company, its value can be labeled as its "Workforce in Place." a country's workforce includes both the employed and the unemployed. The labor force participation rate, LFPR, is the ratio between the labor force and its overall size. This participation rate is the number of people available to work as a percentage of the total population. The rate

² Recent estimates were 300% going up to 454% (Zreik, 2021).

increased from 1960 to 2000 as women entered the labor force, yet dropped due to COVID-19 (Farnham, 2015; Melkonian, 2020). In Lebanon, the economic crisis caused a high rise in unemployment, with massive turnovers resulting from the economic depression. So, according to past studies (and based on figures from <https://tradingeconomics.com>), rates soared from 7% to over 40% (according to www.libnanews.com). Note: The population is estimated at 6.84 million, but this may include Syrian and Palestinian Refugees (Zreik, 2021).

A.6. Sixth Indicator: Prices²

Farnham (2015) believes that prices can be a good indicator, as namely, through the market basket, economists can predict the PPI (or the CPI) to estimate inflation rates, economic growth rates, and so on. Sadly, we have hard evidence that inflation skyrocketed and GDP decreased to prove that we are in an economic trough (Farnham, 2015).

So, here are the price indicators (estimated monthly) as given by the website:

1. Consumer Price Index CPI (points): 116 points (last estimated December 2019).
2. CPI Housing Utilities (points): 109 points (last estimated December 2019).
3. CPI Transportation (points): 106 points (estimated December 2019).
4. Food Inflation (%): 9.77%: (last estimated December 2019).
5. Inflation Rate Mom (%): 2.71 points (last estimated December 2019).

A.7. Seventh Indicator: Money²

Farnham (2015) defines this. We define this as per the banking sector indicators, namely with the interest rate. So, indicators (estimated monthly, except for the Deposit Interest Rate, which is yearly) as given by the website:

1. Money Supply M0 (LBP Billion): 9,818 billion LBP (last estimated December 2019). The USD equivalent is 6.55 billion USD.
2. Money Supply M1 (LBP Billion): 16,620 billion LBP (last estimated December 2019). The USD equivalent is 11.08 billion USD.
3. Money Supply M2 (LBP Billion): 63,484 billion LBP (last estimated December 2019). The USD equivalent is 42.32 billion USD.
4. Money Supply M3 (LBP Billion): 202,831 billion LBP (last estimated: December 2019). The USD equivalent is 135.22 billion USD.
5. Deposit Interest Rate (%): 7.72% (last estimated: December 2018).
6. Banks Balance Sheet (LBP Billion): 326,797 billion LBP (last estimated: December 2019). The USD equivalent is 217.86 billion USD.
7. Central Bank Balance Sheet (LBP Billion): 213,095 billion LBP (last estimated: December 2019). The USD equivalent is 142.06 billion USD.
8. Loans to Banks (LBP Billion): 20,743 billion LBP (last estimated: December 2019). The USD equivalent is 13.83 billion USD.

A.8. Eighth Indicator: Trade²

Farnham (2015) also defines trade through imports and exports ($NX = N - M$). Current statistics in Lebanon prove that Lebanon imports 90% of its goods (or services) concerning 10% is produced locally. According to many economists who study Lebanese GDP evolution, this seriously impinges on GDP estimation. They claim that we work with 67% efficiency, disregarding the 33% illegal and fraudulent activities, which are not part of the estimation (see: www.libnanews.com; Farnham, 2015).

Here are the indicators:

1. Current Account (USD Million) 1143 million USD (last estimated: November 2019).
2. Current Account to GDP (%): -27% (last estimated: December 2018).
3. Exports (USD Million): 309 million USD (last estimated: November 2019).
4. Imports (USD Million): 1281 million USD (last estimated: November 2019).
5. External Debt (USD Million): 33573 million USD (last estimated: November 2019).
6. Capital Flows: 4410 million USD (last estimated: June 2019).
7. Remittances: 833 million USD (last estimated: June 2019).
8. Gold Reserves: 287 Tons (last estimated: June 2019).
9. Foreign Direct Investment: 125 million USD (last estimated: November 2019).
10. Terrorism Index: 4.39 (last estimated: December 2018).
11. Tourist Arrivals: 208,011 people (last estimated November 2019).

A.9. Ninth Indicator: Government2

Government activity as an indicator, as per subsidies are concerned, are often not counting towards a country's GDP. We utilize this indicator to understand state-induced turnover (Moynihan & Landuyt, 2008). However, according to the definition Mazjoub (2018) puts forth, our government acts unethically, as visibly the Lebanese state, the governments, and the political elite are not transparent.

So, we, as per the scope of this research, will not focus too much attention.

1. Government Debt to GDP (%): 15% (last estimated: December 2018).
2. Government Budget (% of GDP): -11% (last estimated: December 2018).
3. Government Budget Value (LBP Million): -631,831 Million LBP (last estimated: October 2019). The USD equivalent is: -421.22 Million USD.
4. Government Spending (LBP Billion): 13,793 billion LBP (last estimated: December 2018). The USD equivalent is: 13.83 billion USD.
5. Government Revenues (LBP Million): 1,253.23 billion LBP (last estimated: October 2005). The USD equivalent is 835.48 billion USD.
6. Fiscal Expenditure (LBP Billion): 1,885.06 billion LBP (last estimated: October 2019). The equivalent is 1.26 billion USD.
7. Credit Rating: 16 (last estimated: February 2020).
8. Government Debt (LBP Billion): 121,434 billion LBP (last estimated: November 2019). The equivalent is 81 billion USD.
9. Military Expenditure (USD Billion): 2,606 (last estimated: December 2018).

Here are the indicators of Tax:

1. Corporate Tax Rate (%) 17% (last estimated: December 2019).
2. Personal Income Tax Rate (%): 24% (last estimated: December 2019).
3. Sales Tax Rate (%): 11% (last estimated: December 2019).
4. Social Security Rate (%): 25.5% (last estimated: December 2019).
5. Social Security Rate for Companies (%): 22.5% (last estimated: December 2019).
6. Social Security Rate for Employees (%) 3% (last estimated: December 2019).

A.10. Tenth Indicator: Businesses2

Farnham (2015) defines this indicator of all business to business to business to consumer services:

1. Internet Speed (KBps): 2056 KBps (last estimated: March 2017).
2. IP Addresses (IP): 179674 (last estimated: March 2017).

3. Coincident Index (points): 274 points (last estimated: November 2019).
4. Competitiveness Index (Points): 56.29 points (last estimated: December 2019).
5. Competitiveness Rank 88 (last estimated: December 2019).
6. Corruption Index (Points): 28 points (last estimated: December 2019).
7. Corruption Rank: 137th/180 (last estimated December 2019).
8. Ease of Doing Business: 143 (last estimated: December 2019).
9. Electricity Production (Gigawatt-hour) 1141
10. Gigawatts/hour (last estimated: December 2019).
11. Manufacturing PMI (points): 44.9 points (last estimated: January 2020).

A.11. Eleventh Indicator: Consumers

Farnham (2015) and Noaman (2018) define consumers as per their activities. Their wants and needs define the supply and demand relationship, which customers must analyze while purchasing the goods/services to satisfy their wants and needs.

1. Consumer Spending (LBP Billion): 59,149 billion LBP (last estimated: December 2018). The USD equivalent is 39.43 billion USD.
2. Gasoline Prices (USD/Liter): 0.81 USD/liter (January 2020).
3. Private Sector Credit (LBP Billion): 70,814 billion LBP (last estimated: December 2019). The USD equivalent is 47.21 billion USD.